

D5.2

Dissemination, Communication and
Engagement Intermediate Report (M18)

WP5

Ecosystem Building, Outreach & Exploitation

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Abstract

This interim report on 6G-REFERENCE dissemination, communication and engagement strategy outlines the main activities and achievements from March 2024 to June 2025. It provides the latest status of the strategy performance, detailing all the actions implemented in terms of communication, dissemination and ecosystem building, and provides an overview of the next steps.

Keywords

Communication, Dissemination, Engagement, Stakeholders, Sustainability, Ecosystem Building, SNS Collaboration, Outreach

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* Deliverable types:

R: document, report (excluding periodic and final reports).

DEM: demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs.

DEC: websites, patent filings, press and media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: software, technical diagrams, etc.

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Acronyms and definitions

6G-REFERENCE	6G haRdware Enablers For cEll fRee cohEreNt Communications & sEnsing
AFIR	Analog Finite Impulse Response
CTTC	Centre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
EuCNC	European Conference on Networks and Communications
EuMW	European Microwave Week
HWG	Hardware Working Group
IMS	International Microwave Symposium
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
LPTV	Linear Periodically Time-Varying
MoU	Memorandum of understanding
MWC	Mobile World Congress
QR code	Quick Response code
RFIC	Radio Frequency Integrated Circuits
SNS JU	Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking
SNS SB	Smart Networks and Services Steering Board
SNS TB	Smart Networks and Services Technology Board
Tbps	Terabit per second
TMA	Time Modulated Array
TMV WG	Test Measurement and Validation Working Group
WiTaR	Women in Telecommunications and Research
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

This document presents the key activities and achievements of 6G haRdware Enablers For cEll fRee cohEreNt Communications & sEnsing (6G-REFERENCE) dissemination, communication and engagement strategy from March 2024 to June 2025.

It outlines the progress made toward enhancing project visibility, stakeholder engagement, and the dissemination of scientific and technological outcomes, providing a comprehensive assessment of its performance.

In the last year, 6G-REFERENCE implemented a strategy focused on building awareness, fostering community engagement, and supporting the adoption of project outcomes. Consequently, the project has successfully established a strong digital presence, including an official website, active social media, biannual newsletters, and an open-access repository on Zenodo.

The consortium has also participated in major events such as the Mobile World Congress (MWC), the European Conference on Networks and Communications (EuCNC) & 6G Summit, and the Radio Frequency Integrated Circuits (RFIC) Symposium. As a full hardware design cycle easily takes more than a year, most results are expected in the last year, 2026. Nevertheless, some first scientific articles in prestigious journals have been published. Moreover, collaborations have been initiated with sister projects and the broader SNS JU ecosystem.

Looking ahead, 6G-REFERENCE will transition into the third strategic phase of its communication, dissemination and engagement plan. As the project matures, the focus will increasingly shift towards the production of scientific outputs and the expansion of its community of stakeholders. The efforts made so far have enhanced the visibility of the project while laying the necessary groundwork to boost the long-term impact of 6G-REFERENCE and its valuable contribution to the next-generation of communication technologies.

1. Introduction

The success and sustainability of disruptive innovations lie to a great extent in the awareness and overall engagement built around them. An effective communication, dissemination, and engagement strategy is critical to boost the visibility of the results and achievements beyond the project's end.

The 6G-REFERENCE Communication, Dissemination, and Engagement Strategy follows a multi-faceted and multi-channel approach, with content and tools tailored to the target audience's specific needs, interests, and engagement potential. It seeks to ensure an active involvement of key stakeholders in the project, building a committed community that can leverage networking opportunities for future developments, as well as promote the outcomes of the project.

This document contains the 6G-REFERENCE dissemination, communication, and engagement intermediate report. It provides a detailed overview of all activities, developments, and outcomes of the activities encompassed in the project strategy between March 2024 and June 2025.

1.1. Main objectives

The objective of the 6G-REFERENCE outreach strategy is to raise awareness about the project and its outcomes, streamlining the collaboration value with key stakeholders, and capitalising on the results generated.

The specific objectives include:

- Establishing and implementing an agile ecosystem framework to identify and create synergies with target stakeholders.
- Defining and executing an effective dissemination and communication strategy to enhance the visibility of project results among a broad and diverse audience, including both academic and non-academic stakeholders such as industry professionals, policymakers, and citizens.
- Facilitate the transfer of knowledge ensuring that the research conducted by 6G-REFERENCE and its findings are accessible and driving the adoption of project outcomes by the European 6G and microelectronics community.

1.2. Outline

The purpose of this document is to report the activities and results of the tasks encompassed in the 6G-REFERENCE Communication, Dissemination, and Engagement Strategy between March 2024 to June 2025 (M06-M18), and how these contributed to the overall objectives of the project.

The document is structured as follows:

- **Chapter 1. Introduction** details the main objectives of the 6G-REFERENCE Communication, Dissemination, and Engagement Strategy and the layout of the document.

- **Chapter 2. Communication and dissemination strategy** presents the performance review of the strategy, provides the latest status of the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and discusses the overall progress towards the objectives set.
- **Chapter 3. Dissemination, communication and engagement activities** delves into the main activities carried out by 6G-REFERENCE between M06-M18.
- **Chapter 4. Conclusions** outlines the main outcomes of the 6G-REFERENCE strategy as well as the next steps to undertake in the upcoming year to fulfil the objectives.

All activities have been carried out in close cooperation with the consortium partners, ensuring alignment with the different tasks of the project that guarantees a seamless operational flow in the implementation of the project and the accomplishment of its goals.

2. Communication and dissemination strategy

This chapter presents a critical assessment of the performance of the Communication and Dissemination Strategy based on the 6G-REFERENCE Impact Plan (D5.1 – Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication Plan).

2.1. Overall strategy performance review

From March 2024 to June 2025, the **6G-REFERENCE Consortium** invested significant efforts into communication and dissemination activities, which play a crucial role in the overall project’s workplan and strategy performance.

Table 1 shows the current status of the KPIs in M18¹.

Table 1. KPIs status in June 2025 (M18)

Type of KPI	Material	Target KPI (M36)	Status (M18)
Communication	Press Release	1+	1
	Website Traffic	100 unique visitors/month	286
	Social media	+2000 followers	989
		+1500 impressions	101,392
	Non-Scientific Articles	50	54
	Open Access Downloads	1000+	749
	Webinars & Workshops	6+ webinars & workshops	1
		300+ participants	30
	Insight Paper	1	0
	Newsletters	12	17
Dissemination	Peer-Reviewed Publications	15	7
		500+ citations	
	Conferences & Events	15+	7
Ecosystem Building	Networks of Contact points	1500+	1,000
	Synergies	4+	1

Monitoring the progress of the communication and dissemination plan is essential to the project success. This proactive and systematic approach allows to identify potential deviations well in advance and to implement the necessary measures to prevent and/or mitigate them. The assessment of the activities’ results also leads to a better understanding of their impact, enabling a swift integration of the learnings into the plan, and ensuring its effectiveness.

¹ Note: the figures were collected in mid-June 2025.

As outlined in the 6G-REFERENCE Impact Plan, the roll-out of communication and dissemination activities was planned in three stages running almost in parallel.

2.1.1. Communication plan assessment and next steps

The central aim of the 6G-REFERENCE Communication Plan is to raise awareness of the project and its outcomes beyond its core community. The Plan follows the communication principles defined by the European Commission.

Plan and revisit (M01 -M06)

During its first six months, 6G-REFERENCE refined the initial communication plan, established its brand, set up the main communication tools and channels (website and social media), and produced its first stakeholder map. The implementation of internal communication tools among the Consortium partners were also developed in this phase. The results were reported in deliverable 5.2.

Early bird communication (M07-M18)

From M09, efforts were dedicated to raising awareness about the project and its current and forthcoming activities to a wider audience, conveying the results to a wider audience in an accessible format. Moreover, the project initiated the first contacts with peer projects and other actors in the SNS ecosystem. It also worked on a first batch of promotional materials, both in visual and written format.

Targeted communication (M19 – M36)

This phase will start approximately in M19, as the project matures and produces its first results. Activities devised include the production of written pieces on specific project outcomes and milestones; the participation in relevant events; and, the launch of social media campaigns, among others.

2.2. Dissemination plan assessment and next steps

While the communication activities were the focus in these 18 months, 6G-REFERENCE also laid the grounds for optimising the dissemination of the scientific and technological project outcomes. Several activities have been already implemented, in particular, the participation in scientific events.

Phase I: Analysis (M01 – M09)

From January 2024 to September 2024, 6G-REFERENCE fine-tuned the initial dissemination plan, assessing priorities and defining a comprehensive set of activities, in alignment with the stakeholder needs, within its domain. Further developing the rapport between the Consortium partners was emphasised, as well as the project's integration in the different SNS JU structures, especially the Working Groups (WGs). The result is available in D5.1.

Phase II: Increase Impact (M10-M18)

The main objective of Phase II is to amplify the impact and awareness generated during the previous phase by showcasing the accomplishments of 6G-REFERENCE. For this purpose, the Consortium leveraged the existing partner's collaboration with key

stakeholders whilst also engaging with new target players identified in the stakeholder map to maximise the impact of the project results.

Phase III – Adoption (M19-M36)

Phase III is expected to start after summer 2025. It will leverage the results of previous phases to continue to attract potential users and costumers through the dissemination of the knowledge and outputs produced by 6G-REFERENCE. The project will ramp up the production of papers and the participation in conferences and other scientific events to ensure the work carried out has a lasting impact. Phase III will be executed in conjunction with the ongoing engagement strategy.

3. Dissemination, communication and engagement activities M06 – M18

6G-REFERENCE implemented a wide range of communication and dissemination activities in the M06-M18 period. Given that communication and dissemination are closely intertwined, the activities are jointly reported hereafter.

3.1. Digital Channels

In the current landscape, digital tools constitute the foundation of any effective communication strategy. 6G-REFERENCE has dedicated significant resources to develop these. Beyond highlighting the project's activities and results, digital channels are crucial to build the 6G-REFERENCE community and positioning it as a reference in the smart networks and services domain.

3.1.1. 6G-REFERENCE Website

6G-REFERENCE's website (6greference.eu) is the main project gateway. Operational since March 2024, it showcases the project's vision, research activities, team, news and events, **Figure 1**.

Figure 1. 6G-REFERENCE website "Home Page"

Besides the Home page, containing information about 6G-REFERENCE's deployments, objectives, challenges, methodologies and news, the website has been structured in five major sections, **Figure 2**.

Figure 2. Tree representing the structure of the 6G-REFERENCE website

1. About

This section contains detailed information about the 6G-REFERENCE project, organised in five subpages:

- [The Project](#) explains what 6G-REFERENCE is, our vision and our impacts at scientific, economic and social levels, **Figure 3**.

Figure 3. About the project: what, why and vision

- **Objectives** offers an overview of the main 6G-REFERENCE objectives, **Figure 4**.

The 6G-REFERENCE Objectives

Figure 4. 6G-REFERENCE objectives

- **Methodology** details why 6G-REFERENCE uses cell-free deployments, joint communication and sensing, and operates at the 10-15GHz range. It also includes information about the challenges addressed by the project, **Figure 5**

Figure 5. 6G-REFERENCE webpage showcasing the challenges

- **The Team** showcases the 10 research and industrial partners from eight European countries. This page was launched in February 2025 (M14), after the partners signed the Consortium Agreement, **Figure 6**.

Figure 6. 6G-REFERENCE website "Team" page

- **6G-REFERENCE Lexicon:** It includes some technical terms and concepts used by the 6G-REFERENCE innovators, **Figure 7**.

Figure 7. 6G-REFERENCE website "Lexicon" page

2. **Activities:** This page is updated monthly serving as the blog or news section of the 6G-REFERENCE website. The articles uploaded are divided into multiple categories news, events, newsletters and other, **Figure 8**.

Figure 8. 6G-REFERENCE website "Activities" page

3. **Publications:** This page gets updated according to the project activities. It is used as a repository for visitors to download public resources from the

project, such as scientific publications and posters, public deliverables, and other communication and dissemination materials, **Figure 9**.

Figure 9. 6G-REFERENCE website “Publications” page

- 4. Community:** This page highlights our relationship with the SNS JU ecosystem, **Figure 10**.

Figure 10. 6G-REFERENCE website “Community” page

- 5. Let's Connect:** This page is a contact form for visitors to get in touch for more information about 6G-REFERENCE, **Error! Reference source not found.**

Your name

Your email

Subject

Your message (optional)

I agree with the [Cookie Policy](#) and the [Privacy Policy](#)

Submit

Contact Us

For media and public relations inquiries, please email: info@6greference.eu

> Would you like to invite us to an event, workshop or initiative? We are all ears!

Figure 11. 6G-REFERENCE website “Let’s connect” page

In the upcoming months, a new page showcasing the 6G-REFERENCE demo cases will be created.

Since its launch in March 2024 (M3), **the website has accumulated a total of 4.292 page views** from April 2024 (M4) to the 15th of June 2025 (M18), averaging 286 page views per month.

Figure 12 shows the traffic of the 6G-REFERENCE website, with clear peaks in June 2024 (569 page views), the month of the EuCNC & 6G Summit; in November 2024 (354), corresponding to the plenary meeting held hosted by ETH Zürich in the Swiss city; and at the end of January 2025 (403), when the 6G-IA Women in Telecommunications and Research (WiTaR) Working Group 2024 Activity Report was shared in the web.

Figure 12. 6G-REFERENCE website traffic

This means that events, project meetings and reports produced by the SNS JU community constitute the main source of traffic.

A total of 611 unique users have visited the 6G-REFERENCE website during this reporting period. They usually stay 1m 43s reading the content of our website. The top five pages visited are shown in **Table 2**.

Table 2. Top 5 visited pages in 6G-REFERENCE website

Website Page	Page Views	Link
Home	1.369	Link

Activities	492	Link
Publications	322	Link
The Project	259	Link
6G-REFERENCE Lexicon	194	Link

Most visitors that arrive to the 6G-REFERENCE website come from direct traffic (64.32%), meaning they access the site typing the URL directly or using a bookmark. This is followed by organic search (24.06%), where users find the site through search engines like Google. Organic social traffic (14.4%) reflects unpaid visits coming from social media. Lastly, referrals (5.89%) comprise users that access the site via links from other websites, excluding social media and search engines. As it can be observed in **Figure 13**, the majority of users come from the United States (17.35%), Spain (14.89%), Germany (7.53%), China (5.73%) and the United Kingdom (5.24%).

Figure 13. Country of visitors 6G-REFERENCE website

3.1.2. Social Media

6G-REFERENCE’s social media is the cornerstone of the project’s daily communication and dissemination efforts. Active on LinkedIn, X (formerly Twitter) and BlueSky, **6G-REFERENCE’s social media community has reached 989 followers, nearly 50% of the target** of 2,000 followers by the end of the project.

Out of this 989 followers, most are on LinkedIn (805), with the rest coming from X (120) and BlueSky (64), **Table 3**. Posts on LinkedIn and X accumulate a total of 101,392 impressions², averaging 5,964 monthly impressions. **This figure is well above the initial target of 1,500+ impressions per month.** Most of the impressions come from LinkedIn (92,314), and a smaller part from X (9,078).

Table 3. 6G-REFERENCE online community

LinkedIn	X	BlueSky
@6G-REFERENCE	@6G Reference	@6g-reference.bsky.social

² BlueSky does not allow to track the impressions of the posts.

805 followers	120 followers	64 followers
92,314 impressions	9,078 impressions	N/A

While 6G-REFERENCE was present in X and LinkedIn, the decision to open a third social media profile in BlueSky was made in January 2025 (M13). This was mainly due to the widespread disinformation and misinformation affecting X, and the subsequent loss of users, and the need to reach a wider audience.

Figure 14 and **Figure 15** show the 6G-REFERENCE profiles in its social media accounts.

Figure 14. 6G-REFERENCE LinkedIn profile

Figure 15. 6G-REFERENCE profile in BlueSky (left) and X (right)

LinkedIn followers come mainly from Spain, Switzerland, United Kingdom, Greece, India, France, The Netherlands, Germany, Italy and Sweden. Almost half of them (47.2%) come from education and research jobs. The main industries of our followers are software development, research services, higher education, telecommunications, and IT services and consulting, which indicates that the communication and dissemination activities are reaching the target audience, **Figure 16**

Visitor demographics

Figure 16. 6G-REFERENCE LinkedIn visitors demographics

Social media campaigns

The project posts three times per week on average in LinkedIn, X and Bluesky. Usually, this entails sharing publications related to the project and its activities, project news, articles and newsletters; promoting its participation in events and post-event recaps; publishing partner interviews to present their organisation and role in the consortium; but also disseminating information about the project's methodology, research outcomes and objectives, as well as about the SNS JU community and the 6G ecosystem.

The content is tailored to the platform and organised in ad hoc social media campaigns, as detailed below.

6G-REFERENCE brand awareness – promotion of the project website, newsletter, lexicon, methodology, challenges, impacts and objectives, **Figure 17**.

Figure 17. Examples of posts about the lexicon, methodology and challenges

6G-REFERENCE partners – promotion of the consortium partners and their role in the project, **Figure 18** and **Figure 19**.

Figure 18. Examples of posts as part of the 6G-REFERENCE partners' campaign

Figure 19. Examples of posts as part of the 6G-REFERENCE partners' campaign (interviews)

6G-REFERENCE events (pre, during, and post-event updates), **Figure 20** and **Figure 21**.

Figure 20. Campaign covering 6G-REFERENCE participation in the MWC 2025

Figure 21. Campaign covering 6G-REFERENCE participation in the EuCNC & 6G Summit 2025

6G-REFERENCE research dissemination – diffusion of scientific publications, scientific posters and deliverables, **Figure 22.**

Figure 22. Example of posts disseminating 6G-REFERENCE research outcomes

6G-REFERENCE Press Releases, news and articles, Figure 23.

Figure 23. Example of a post sharing an article explaining the 6G-REFERENCE project

SNS JU and 6G ecosystem – promotion of the latest news, opportunities and events in the SNS community and the overall 6G ecosystem, Figure 24.

Figure 24. Examples of posts and reposts disseminating content about the SNS JU community

Regarding the impact and performance of these campaigns, it has been observed that usually, content related to events, project meetings and relevant reports have a better performance with more engagement (likes, comments and reposts) that brings traffic to the 6G-REFERENCE website, as it was previously indicated.

3.1.3. Videos

6G-REFERENCE is active on YouTube (@6G-REFERENCE), **Figure 25**.

Figure 25. 6G-REFERENCE profile in YouTube

During the first six months of 2025, the project has started to upload a series of video interviews to introduce the project partners, under the title [“6G-REFERENCE Interview Series - Meet our Partners!”](#), **Figure 26**. Six videos have been uploaded thus far and four more will be released in the upcoming months to introduce the ten partners forming the 6G-REFERENCE consortium.

Figure 26. title “6G-REFERENCE Interview Series - Meet our Partners!”

The six videos published during this reporting period gathered a total of 296 views, **Table 4**. The channel has six subscribers.

Table 4. 6G-REFERENCE videos in YouTube

Video	Views	Link
6G-REFERENCE Project Interview Series - Dominique Morche - CEA-Leti	23	https://youtu.be/ta_bW4pVon0?feature=shared
6G-REFERENCE Project Interview Series - Marc Bauduin - IMEC	14	https://youtu.be/HziSalU_5aE?feature=shared
6G-REFERENCE Project Interview Series - Itziar Maestrojuán - Anteral	49	https://youtu.be/4caTxh - YPQ?feature=shared
6G-REFERENCE Project Interview Series - Hua Wang - ETH Zürich	144	https://youtu.be/BwD5oRB RiWw?feature=shared
6G-REFERENCE Project Interview Series - Ignacio Llamas, Coordinator - CTTC	23	https://youtu.be/2v9O6yM whTA?feature=shared
6G-REFERENCE Project Interview Series - Eric Klumperink, Technical Manager - University of Twente	43	https://youtu.be/44YfleX89 Wc?feature=shared

In the next reporting period, 6G-REFERENCE plans to produce video interviews with the PhD students working on the project, as well as video presentations and recaps for its demo cases and event participation (e.g. EuCnC) when relevant.

3.1.4. Open Access Repository – Zenodo

6G-REFERENCE is committed to Open Science. Its Zenodo community and repository provides access to peer-reviewed publications, public deliverables, and other resources produced within the project.

The 6G-REFERENCE repository at Zenodo contains 19 publications, from scientific papers, deliverables and presentations to promotional materials. These accumulate 978 views and 749 downloads so far. The most popular publication currently is the press release “The 6G-REFERENCE Project Kicks-Off to Offer a Sustainable Solution Based on 6G Hardware Enablers For Cell Free Coherent Communications and Sensing in Urban Areas” with 225 views and 122 downloads, **Table 5**.

Table 5. 6G-REFERENCE publications in Zenodo

Publication	Link
Radio Frequency Low-Cost Temperature Sensor (poster)	https://zenodo.org/records/15722933
Planar Low-Cost Microwave Ring Resonator Temperature Sensor using a PDMS Active Layer	https://zenodo.org/records/15698205
Time Modulated Array and Time Variant Filter Techniques to Reduce Receiver Hardware Complexity and Power Consumption	https://zenodo.org/records/15698096
Time Modulated Arrays and Time Variant Filter Techniques to Reduce Hardware Complexity and Power Consumption - EuCNC 2025	https://zenodo.org/records/15697887
Radio Frequency Low-Cost Temperature Sensor	https://zenodo.org/records/15697847
A D-Band Scalable and LO-Less Time-Modulated Multibeam Active Relay Array With Broadcasting Capability for 6G Distributed MIMO Networks	https://zenodo.org/records/15697680

Publication	Link
Highly Linear Time-Variant Mixers/Filters: Operation and Analysis	https://zenodo.org/records/15697492
6G-REFERENCE - Roll-up - 2025 Version	https://zenodo.org/records/15119040
6G-REFERENCE - Flyer - 2025 Version	https://zenodo.org/records/15119133
A D-Band Concurrent 20-Beam MIMO Transmitter Array with A Four-Element Joint Static/Dynamic Beam-Multiplication Beamformer	https://zenodo.org/records/14906732
A Programmable Filtering and Frequency Translation by Aliasing IF Receiver with Alias- and Harmonic-Rejection	https://zenodo.org/records/14906792
Low-Coherence Sequence Design Under PAPR Constraints	https://zenodo.org/records/14860318
D1.1 - Distributed Radio Specification (M8)	https://zenodo.org/records/15082421
D5.1 - Dissemination, Exploitation & Communication Plans (M6)	https://zenodo.org/records/15082383
6G-REFERENCE Project Poster for EuCNC Conference (2)	https://zenodo.org/records/14278918
6G-REFERENCE Project Poster for EuCNC Conference (1)	https://zenodo.org/records/14278876
Press Release: The 6G-REFERENCE Project Kicks-Off to Offer a Sustainable Solution Based on 6G Hardware Enablers For Cell Free Coherent Communications and Sensing in Urban Areas	https://zenodo.org/records/10723721
6G-REFERENCE - BrandBook	https://zenodo.org/records/10804367
6G-REFERENCE EU Project - Promotion Material - Roll-up	https://zenodo.org/records/10804016
6G-REFERENCE EU Project - Promotion Material - Flyer	https://zenodo.org/records/10803936

The most popular publication currently is the press release “The 6G-REFERENCE Project Kicks-Off to Offer a Sustainable Solution Based on 6G Hardware Enablers For Cell Free Coherent Communications and Sensing in Urban Areas”³ with 225 views and 122 downloads.

3.1.5. 6G-REFERENCE Newsletter

6G-REFERENCE’s newsletters are published every six months via [LinkedIn](#) and the 6G-REFERENCE website. LinkedIn was chosen as the main platform to release the newsletters due to our community of over 800 followers, which maximises the impact of any targeted communication action. The 6G-REFERENCE newsletter has 330 subscribers on LinkedIn, **Figure 27** Moreover, the newsletters are shared on X and BlueSky.

³ Press release available at: <https://zenodo.org/records/10723721>

Figure 27. 6G-REFERENCE LinkedIn newsletter

Since June 2024 (M6), the project has published two newsletters, **Table 6**.

Table 6. 6G-REFERENCE newsletters

Newsletter	Date	Link
6G-REFERENCE Project Newsflash #2 - January 2025: New Year, New Use Cases on 6G Communications, Sensing and Synchronization	23/01/2025	LinkedIn article Website article
6G-REFERENCE Project Newsflash #1 - June 2024: 6G Sustainable Solutions for Cell Free Coherent Communications & Sensing in Urban Areas	20/06/2024	LinkedIn article Website article

The 6G-REFERENCE newsletters summarise the main project activities during the six months prior to their release. They include articles about the project meetings, milestones and achievements as published on the website, as well as information related to the events attended by the partners.

They also highlight the 6G-REFERENCE relation to the SNS JU ecosystem and our sister projects, explaining why and how we are part of it, and sharing some reports and documents, such as the *SNS Journal 2024* or the *The WiTaR Working Group 2024 Report*.

Figure 28 illustrates some examples of the 6G-REFERENCE newsletter as seen in different channels.

Figure 28. 6G-REFERENCE newsletter example

The first newsletter published on LinkedIn generated 1,767 impressions and reached 450 members, while the second created 1,120 impressions and reached 563 members. The latter was also delivered by email to 161 subscribers, with a 43% email open rate. In total, the first two newsletters were read by 427 users.

The next edition is due in July 2025 (M19) and will include two new sections: one showcasing the partners' interviews published on YouTube and another one about the scientific publications. This flexible structure allows to adapt the newsletter to the project's evolution and its needs, ensuring an optimal dissemination of 6G-REFERENCE's research results.

Furthermore, 6G-REFERENCE has published articles about the project in 15 external newsletters, mainly through its Communication, Dissemination and Engagement partner AUSTRALO and the SNS JU, **Figure 29**.

SNS JU PROJECT NEWS:

6G-XR SECOND ROUND OF OPEN CALL

6G-XR officially launched the second round of its Open Call to SNS JU Stream B projects with €60,000 to complement the 6G-XR experimental platforms and research infrastructures.

The Call is open to SNS JU Stream B projects working in the following topics:

- System Architecture (HORIZON-JU-SNS-2022-STREAM-B-01-01)
- Wireless Communication Technologies and Signal Processing (HORIZON-JU-SNS-2022-STREAM-B-01-02)
- Communication Infrastructure Technologies and Devices (HORIZON-JU-SNS-2022-STREAM-B-01-03)
- Secure Service development and Smart Security (HORIZON-JU-SNS-2022-STREAM-B-01-04)
- 6G Holistic System (HORIZON-JU-SNS-2022-STREAM-B-01-05)

[Read more](#)

6G-REFERENCE PROJECT KICK-OFF

On 29 February 2024, the 6G-REFERENCE project has been launched. The project, 6G Hardware Enablers for Cell Free Coherent Communications and Sensing, envisions a future where urban areas are equipped with sustainable solutions that can cope with the ever-increasing traffic demands and population densification, while providing disruptive capabilities like the materialization of the internet of sense.

6G-REFERENCE is an innovation and research project running for 3 years, until December 2026, funded by the Horizon Europe Program of the European Commission, and part of Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU). The project is a joint collaboration of 10 research and industry partners from 8 European countries.

[Read more](#)

Figure 29. Article about 6G-REFERENCE in the SNS JU newsflash

3.2. Publications

3.2.1. Scientific Publications

As of June 2025, 6G-REFERENCE has produced four journal papers and four conference papers, totalling eight peer-reviewed publications, **Table 7**. All papers are available in Zenodo and the 6G-REFERENCE website.

Table 7. List of 6G-REFERENCE scientific publications

Type	Title	Link
Journal	K. -S. Choi, B. Abdelaziz Abdelmagid, Y. Liu and H. Wang, "A D-Band Concurrent 20-Beam MIMO Transmitter Array With a Four-Element Joint Static/Dynamic Beam-Multiplication Beamformer," in IEEE Journal of Solid-State Circuits , vol. 60, no. 6, pp. 1906-1920, June 2025, doi: 10.1109/JSSC.2024.3487619	https://zenodo.org/records/14906732
Journal	B. A. Abdelmagid, K. -S. Choi, Y. Kim and H. Wang, "A D-Band Scalable and LO-Less Time-Modulated Multibeam Active Relay Array With Broadcasting Capability for 6G Distributed MIMO Networks," in IEEE Transactions on Microwave Theory and Techniques , doi: 10.1109/TMTT.2025.3568127	https://zenodo.org/records/15697680
Journal	V. Kendae Ramkumar, M. Huiskamp, H. Singh Bindra, E. Klumperink and B. Nauta, "A Programmable Filtering and Frequency Translation by Aliasing IF Receiver With Alias and Harmonic Rejection," in IEEE Journal of Solid-State Circuits , vol. 60, no. 6, pp. 1997-2012, June 2025, doi: 10.1109/JSSC.2024.3481879	https://zenodo.org/records/14906792

Type	Title	Link
Journal	G. Sun, W. Wang, W. Xu and C. Studer, "Low-Coherence Sequence Design Under PAPR Constraints," in IEEE Wireless Communications Letters , vol. 13, no. 12, pp. 3663-3667, Dec. 2024, doi: 10.1109/LWC.2024.3485818	https://zenodo.org/records/14860318
Conference paper	V. Kendae Ramkumar, B.A. Abdelmagid, H.S. Bindra, H. Wang, E.A.M. Klumperink, " Time Modulated Array and Time Variant Filter Techniques Trading Radio Performance and Power " <i>European Conference on Networks and Communications, 3-6 June 2025, Poznan, Poland</i>	https://zenodo.org/records/15698096
Conference paper	Rasoul Fakhteh, Yi-Wen Wu, Yi Wang, " Water-Controlled 1-bit Reconfigurable Surface " <i>European MicroWave Week (EuMW 2025), 21– 26 September 2025, Utrecht, Netherlands</i>	n.a.
Conference paper	Zabdiel Brito-Brito; Jesús Salvador Velázquez-González; Fermín Mira; Yi Wang; Ignacio Llamas-Garro, " Planar Low-Cost Microwave Ring Resonator Temperature Sensor using a PDMS Active Layer " <i>European Microwave Week (EuMW 2025), 21– 26 September 2025, Utrecht, Netherlands</i>	https://zenodo.org/records/15698205

3.2.2. Awareness Publications

6G-REFERENCE has produced a total of 54 online awareness, or non-scientific, publications. These tackle a variety of topics, from accounts of the plenary meetings and events to new papers and activities and accumulate 1.016 views in total, **Table 8**

Table 8. List of selected awareness publications (in bold those most viewed)

Title & Link	Date
6G-REFERENCE at the SNS JU Journal 2025	16/06/2025
The 6G-REFERENCE Partner University of Birmingham Presents a Scientific Poster at Metamaterials UK Conference & Forum 2025	13/06/2025
The 6G-REFERENCE Partners Present our Preliminary Research Results and Join Discussions on 6G Topics at the EuCNC & 6G Summit 2025	11/06/2025
6G-REFERENCE Presents its Research Activities with a Poster and a Publication at the EuCNC & 6G Summit 2025	26/05/2025
The 6G-REFERENCE Consortium Gathers in Enschede in our Third Meeting to Discuss our Half-Way Report Status and Demo Definitions	13/05/2025
6G-REFERENCE Showcases Our Research & Development Progress to SNS JU and European Commission Leaders at MWC 2025	13/03/2025
6G-IA Women in Telecommunications and Research (WiTaR) Working Group Publishes their 2024 Activity Report	22/01/2025
The 6G-REFERENCE Partners Meet in Person for the Second time in Zurich to Review the Project Status	13/11/2024
What is 6G-REFERENCE? The EU Project Deploying 6G Sustainable Solutions for Cell Free Coherent Communications and Sensing	29/08/2024
Why 6G-REFERENCE is a SNS JU Project Boosting 6G Research in Europe	13/08/2024

Title & Link	Date
The SNS Journal 2024 Features the 6G-REFERENCE Project	19/06/2024
6G-REFERENCE Presents the Project Goals at the EuCNC & 6G Summit 2024	11/06/2024
6G-REFERENCE Poster: The Project Activities and Goals	10/06/2024
6G-REFERENCE Poster: Vision, Hardware Solutions and Challenges	10/06/2024
The 6G-REFERENCE Flyer and Roll-up: 6G Hardware Enablers for Cell Free Coherent Communications and Sensing	29/05/2024
The 6G-REFERENCE Partners Meet at the First General Assembly and Face-to-face Kick-off Meeting to Discuss the Project Research Objectives	26/04/2024
6G-REFERENCE First Presentation: Our Coordinator Ignacio Llamas Introduces the Project at the SNS JU & 6G-IA Webinar to Showcase the Call 2 Projects	15/03/2024
6G-REFERENCE Attends its First Event: The Mobile World Congress 2024 in Barcelona	01/03/2024
Press Release: The 6G-REFERENCE Project Kicks-Off to Offer a Sustainable Solution Based on 6G Hardware Enablers For Cell Free Coherent Communications and Sensing in Urban Areas	28/02/2024
The 6G-REFERENCE Partners Host the Project Virtual Pre-kick Off Meeting to Present their Work Packages	22/01/2024

Out of the 54 awareness publications, 17 are newsletters, 20 are blog articles published on the 6G-REFERENCE website (including the press release about the kick-off meeting of the project) and 17 are external articles published on other websites and media outlets, **Figure 30**. As of M18 (June 2024), the KPI of 50 non-scientific publications has been reached.

Figure 30. Example of awareness publications in the 6G-REFERENCE website

Regarding the external articles published on other websites, there are 11 pieces, published mainly by the Centre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya, 6G-REFERENCE coordinator, and the Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU), **Table 9** and **Figure 31**.

Table 9. Selected external articles

Title & Link	Publisher
SNS JU Journal 2025	SNS JU
6G-REFERENCE: Building Hardware Foundations for Distributed 6G Systems	Free 6G Training
Key Insights from the SNS JU Session at MWC25	SNS JU
SNS JU projects showcase innovation at Mobile World Congress 2025	SNS JU
SNS Journal 2024	SNS JU
6G-REFERENCE	EuCNC & 6G Summit
6G research gets €130 million EU funding boost in Europe	European Commission
CTTC participates in 6G-REFERENCE to advance 6G research in Europe	CTTC
6G RESEARCH GETS A 130 MILLION EUR EU FUNDING BOOST IN EUROPE	SNS JU
6G REFERENCE - Factory joint sensing and communications	SNS JU
6G REFERENCE - Factory scenario	SNS JU

CENTRE TECNOLÒGIC DE TELECOMUNICACIONS DE CATALUNYA (CTTC) is proud to announce it will coordinate the project titled 6G haRdware Enablers For cElli fRee cohEreNt Communications & sEnsing (6G-REFERENCE) from the latest **Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU)** call for proposals. This project is set to develop innovative solutions for 6G technologies in Europe.

CENTRE TECNOLÒGIC DE TELECOMUNICACIONS DE CATALUNYA (CTTC) is excited to embark on its new SNS JU project, 6G haRdware Enablers For cElli fRee cohEreNt Communications & sEnsing (6G-REFERENCE), which is set to commence on January 1, 2024. The project aims to develop hardware enablers constituting a reference design of distributed radios for a cell-free communication and sensing system operating in the 10-15 GHz range. It targets low complexity and low power, in other words, practical integrated circuits (IC) and antenna systems for 6G applications. Thus, it aims at enabling new functionalities addressing D-MIMO communication

Figure 31. Example of an article published by CTTC about 6G-REFERENCE

The 6G-REFERENCE project has also had an impact on international media outlets from Europe, UK and Australia. A total of six clippings have been published until June 2025 (M18), **Table 10**.

Table 10. Clippings about 6G-REFERENCE

Title & Link	Media Outlet	Date
6G-REFERENCE project envisions cell-free comms in urban areas	Critical Comms	29/04/2024
La segunda convocatoria de SNS JU selecciona 27 proyectos de investigación e innovación en 6G	Casa Domo	23/10/2023
€130m for 27 6G projects in Europe	EE News Europe	20/10/2023
Financiación de 130 millones de euros de fondos europeos para 27 proyectos de investigación en 6G	Esmartcity.es	20/10/2023
6G research gets a 130 million EUR EU funding boost in Europe	Cyprus Shipping News	20/10/2023
EU hands over €130 million for 6G research	Telecoms	19/10/2023

3.3. Outreach Activities

3.3.1. Scientific events

In the last 18 months, 6G-REFERENCE participated in four renowned conferences, both in Europe and in the United States. In addition to fostering relationships with its peers, the project presented various papers and posters.

EuCNC & 6G Summit “From vision to reality”, 3-6.06.2024, Antwerp, Belgium

6G-REFERENCE attended its first EuCNC edition in 2024, where it presented a poster⁴ showing the project’s vision, motivation, objectives, challenges and activities, **Figure 32**.

⁴ Poster available at: <https://zenodo.org/records/14278876>

Figure 32. Ignacio Llamas, CTC and project coordinator (left) and Eric Klumperink, University of Twente and technical coordinator (right).

Eric Klumperink delivered a presentation emphasising 6G-REFERENCE’s vision in which urban areas are equipped with sustainable solutions that can cope with the ever-increasing traffic demands and population densification, while providing disruptive capabilities like the materialization of the internet of senses⁵.

Link: <https://www.eucnc.eu/>

Metamaterials UK Conference & Forum 2025, 20-22.05.2025, Tortworth, UK

The University of Birmingham (UB) represented 6G-REFERENCE in the Metamaterials Conference. It presented a poster highlighting the recent work on reconfigurable metasurfaces and a demo of a RIS.

Link: <https://metamaterials.network/conference-forum-2025/>

EuCNC & 6G Summit "Towards the 6G World", 3-6.06.2025, Poznan, Poland

6G-REFERENCE participated for the second year in a row at the EuCNC & 6G Summit. The project had a very active time at the conference. A poster booth, together with a roll-up, were available to visitors during the event.

Zabdiel Brito (CTTC) presented the poster **“Radio Frequency Low-Cost Temperature Sensor”**⁶ during the dedicated session whilst Viswesh Kendae Ramkumar (University of Twente) presented the paper **“Time Modulated Array and Time Variant Filter Techniques to Reduce Receiver Hardware Complexity and Power Consumption”**⁷ during the PHY-4 track “Transceiver Models and Performance”, **Figure 33**

⁵ Presentation available at: <https://6greference.eu/6g-reference-presents-the-project-goals-at-the-eucnc-6g-summit-2024/>

⁶ Poster available at: <https://zenodo.org/records/15722933>

⁷ Presentation and paper available at: <https://zenodo.org/records/15697887> and <https://zenodo.org/records/15698096>

Figure 33. Viswesh K. Ramkumar during his presentation (source: EuCNC)

Link: <https://www.eucnc.eu/>

2025 IEEE Microwave Theory and Technology Society (MTT-S) International Microwave Symposium (IMS2025), 15-20 June 2025, San Francisco, United States

The UB, representing 6G-REFERENCE, delivered a presentation titled “**Liquid-Metal (LM) Enabled Microwave and Mm-Wave Devices**” in the “Microwave Materials and Processing Technologies for RF Wireless Applications” workshop held on the 16 of June 2025.

Furthermore, Eric Klumperink (University of Twente) delivered a presentation titled “**Highly Linear Time-variant Mixers/Filters: Operation and Analysis**”⁸, discussing TMA and AFIR as time-variant techniques, **Figure 34**. The presentation was part of the workshop co-organised by 6G-REFERENCE “Designing with time: Linear Periodically Time-Varying (LPTV) Circuit Approaches Enabling Advanced RFIC Applications”, held on the 15 of June 2025.

⁸ Presentation available at: <https://zenodo.org/records/15697492>

Figure 34. Eric Klumperink (University of Twente) at his presentation in IMS 2025

Link: <https://ims-ieee.org/>

6G-REFERENCE will attend two more scientific events in the coming months, namely:

- Simposio Nacional de la Unión Científica Internacional de Radio (URSI 2025), September 2025, Tarragona, Spain. The project will co-organise the event and a workshop.

Link: www.ursitarragona2025.es/

- European Microwave Week (EuMW 2025), September 2025, Utrecht, The Netherlands. The project will present two papers: "Planar Low-Cost Microwave Ring Resonator Temperature Sensor using a PDMS Active Layer" and "Water-Controlled 1-bit Reconfigurable Surface".

Link: www.eumw.eu/general-information/

3.3.2. Conference, workshops and events (non-peer reviewed)

6G-REFERENCE participated in two editions of the MWC, one of the most prominent events worldwide in the sector of telecommunications, as well as in a webinar organised by the SNS JU. During these events, the project promoted its work and started conversations about potential collaborations with several initiatives.

Mobile World Congress (MWC) 2024, 26-29.02.2024, Barcelona Spain

The project coordinator, CTTC, represented 6G-REFERENCE in the MWC 2024. It had a booth and a roll-up⁹ presenting an overview of the project¹⁰.

⁹ Roll-up: <https://zenodo.org/records/10804016>

¹⁰ Read more: <https://6greference.eu/6g-reference-attends-its-first-event-the-mobile-world-congress-2024-in-barcelona/>

Link: <https://www.mwcbarcelona.com/>

SNS Webinar - Introducing the Call 2 SNS projects

A two parts webinar was organised to introduce the projects awarded in the second phase of the SNS JU. Ignacio Llamas, CTTC and 6G-REFERENCE coordinator, presented the project alongside the other B5 (Microelectronics-based Solutions for 6G Networks) projects, as well as those in Stream B2 (Wireless Communication Technologies and Signal Processing), B6 (EU-US 6G R&I Cooperation), C (Complementary SNS experimental Pan-EU federated Infrastructure), D (SNS Large Scale Trials and Pilots with Verticals) and the CSA (SNS Societal Challenges).

Link: <https://smart-networks.europa.eu/event/sns-webinar-introducing-the-call-2-sns-projects-part-2-of-2/>

Mobile World Congress (MWC) 2025, 3-6.03.2025, Barcelona Spain

6G-REFERENCE coordinator, CTTC, alongside project partners AUSTRALO and ETH Zurich, participated in the MWC 2025. The project was featured at the CTTC booth, where it was introduced with a roll-up. Visitors also had the opportunity to explore 6G-REFERENCE cutting-edge Research and Development (R&D) results and proofs-of-concept.

Figure 35. Ignacio Llamas, project coordinator, presenting 6G-REFERENCE at the CTTC booth in the MWC 2025

Link: <https://www.mwcbarcelona.com/>

3.4. Promotional material

Since M06, 6G-REFERENCE has focused on consolidating its brand and visual identity. In addition to the banners and many visuals created for the website and social media, the project has also produced several materials to support its promotion during events.

A first promotional roll-up was designed to briefly present the project in a visually appealing format¹¹. The design was updated in 2025 featuring the consortium partners¹². Moreover, a poster was created for EuCNC 2024 showcasing the main aspects of the project, including its vision, objectives, motivation, challenges, activities and goals, **Figure 36** and **Figure 36**.

¹¹ 2024 roll-up available at: <https://zenodo.org/records/10804016>

¹² 2025 roll-up available at: <https://zenodo.org/records/15119040>

6G-REFERENCE

6G haRdware Enablers For cEIl fRee cohEreNt Communications & sEnSIng

6G-REFERENCE vision

6G-REFERENCE focuses on ultra-dense cell-free deployments for joint coherent communications and sensing at cm-waves, which balance the benefits of sub-6GHz (e.g. reduced pathloss) and mm-wave (e.g. wide bandwidth) ranges. 6G-REFERENCE targets transceiver hardware innovations enabling 6G densely distributed systems exploiting distributed MIMO. To allow for flexible deployment, fiber access cannot be taken for granted.

6G-REFERENCE motivation

In urban areas, 6G will need to rely on a sustainable solution to cope with the ever-increasing traffic demands and population densification, while providing disruptive capabilities like the materialization of the internet of sense. Synchronization in frequency and time over the air then becomes a key challenge. Distributed cell-free MIMO systems arise as a promising solution to address required improvements in data capacity, while also supporting distributed sensing functionality. Realizing all this functionality in practical hardware with low complexity, cost, and power consumption is a key challenge. We believe this may be possible exploiting cm-wave 10-15 GHz spectrum.

6G-REFERENCE objectives and hardware solutions

The development of 6G hardware enablers for joint communications and sensing

In-Band MIMO full duplex transceiver innovations

- Data capacity enhancement
- Solving scheduling challenge
- Enabling monostatic radar

Novel synchronization solutions

- For accurate phase/frequency/time sync
- Continuous sync enabled by full duplex (FD SYNC)

Novel RF and antenna components

- Reduced complexity/cost
- Time modulated arrays
- Frequency modulated arrays
- RIS
- Environmental sensors

Dynamic filtering (IF and antenna)

- Frequency selectivity
- Spectrum coexistence (10-15 GHz)

Hardware solutions and their relation to system level improvements and 6G goals

6G-REFERENCE challenges

Five fundamental challenges:

- The need of accurate synchronization among distributed radio units
- Fronthaul data distribution
- Integration of sensing capabilities
- Low complexity/cost/consumption radios
- Coexistence with other services

Figure 36. Poster for EuCNC 2024 (1) designed by AUS

A second poster was created for EuCNC 2025. It delved into 6G-REFERENCE activities and goals and featured the consortium partners, **Figure 37**

6G-REFERENCE

6G-REFERENCE activities and goals

6G-REFERENCE Preliminary baseline architecture

6G-REFERENCE Integrated Circuit Development

6G-REFERENCE Radio unit concept

6G-REFERENCE RF and antenna components

6G-REFERENCE Time Modulated Array – Frequency Modulated Array

Figure 37. Poster for EuCNC 2024 (2) designed by AUS

Two flyers were designed to be distributed at the event, **Figure 38**.

Figure 38. 6G-REFERENCE flyers¹³

The commitment of 6G-REFERENCE to sustainable practices entails that the printing of materials is kept to a minimum, opting for alternative tools such as QR codes to visit and access different 6G-REFERENCE channels and materials.

3.5. Collaboration with the SNS & 6G Ecosystem

3.5.1. Activities – Synergies

During its first year, 6G-REFERENCE focus was mainly inwards. It prioritised laying the foundations for the work to be carried out, and strengthening the relationships between partners, better defining the roles, setting up the necessary mechanisms for collaboration, and implementing the planned activities. The delay in the Consortium Agreement signature also impacted and limited the establishment of activities with external collaborators.

An important milestone during this period was the integration of 6G-REFERENCE in the different bodies of the SNS JU. For instance, the SNS Steering Board (SB), encompassing all SNS JU project coordinators; the SNS Technology Board (TB) comprising all SNS JU project technical managers; and the different SNS Working Groups and Taskforces. Besides the SNS SB and TB, 6G-REFERENCE is active in the SNS JU Hardware WG, the Test, Measurement and KPIs Validation (TMV) WG and the Communications Task Force, as well as in the 6G-Industry Association (6G-IA) Women in Telecommunications and Research (WiTAR) WG.

¹³ Flyers are available at: <https://zenodo.org/records/15119133> and <https://zenodo.org/records/10803936>

Moreover, 6G-REFERENCE participated in flagship events for the SNS community: MWC and EuCNC & 6G Summit, where it promoted its activities and latest developments and engaged with peer projects and relevant stakeholders.

In June 2025, **6G-REFERENCE signed a memorandum of understanding (MoU)¹⁴ with NGI SARGASSO¹⁵**, a project that aims to create a unique collaborative ecosystem to harness EU-US and EU-Canada technology breakthroughs to revolutionise the NextGeneration Internet technologies, services and standards, and contribute to the evolution of the Internet according to a human-centric approach of the internet commons. The MoU establishes a cooperation between the projects to mutually promote each other efforts, mainly centred around standards.

Furthermore, the project has initiated a dialogue with its sister projects in B-01-05: Microelectronics-based Solutions for 6G Networks: Fourier-Domain TRx Solutions Enabling Widespread Realisation of 6G (FirstTo6G)¹⁶ and Towards Energy-Efficient Tbps Wireless Links (TeraGreen)¹⁷. The objective is to organise a joint action to exchange knowledge on topics such as energy efficiency and microelectronics, among others.

6G-REFERENCE is also exploring the possibility to organise a joint webinar with CoreNext¹⁸. The project focuses on anticipated needs of the 6G deployment, especially two key gaps concerning improved energy efficiency and end-to-end trustworthiness from analogue interface to digital processing.

The results of the efforts invested in engaging relevant stakeholders will flourish in the upcoming months.

¹⁴ The MoU is not available yet.

¹⁵ NGI SARGASSO website: <https://ngisargasso.eu/>

¹⁶ FirstTo6G website: <https://firstto6g.eu/>

¹⁷ TeraGreen website: <https://teragreen.eu/>

¹⁸ CoreNext website: <https://corenext.eu/>

4. Conclusions

Communication, dissemination, and engagement activities are essential to guarantee the impact of a project beyond its duration.

In the last year, 6G-REFERENCE has reached important milestones in terms of publications, participation in events and conferences, and the consolidation and growth of its digital presence, boosting the project visibility in and engagement with the SNS ecosystem. Furthermore, it has taken important steps towards forming synergies with peer projects.

Several KPI targets have been met and even surpassed in this first reporting period, including the number of impressions, newsletters, videos and awareness publications. These results reflect an effective outreach strategy aligned with the project objectives.

In the coming year, 6G-REFERENCE will scale up the dissemination and communication efforts, increasing the scientific output and leveraging strategic partnerships with key stakeholders to ensure the sustainability and long-term impact of the work performed.

Overall, the communication, dissemination and engagement efforts carried out to date provide a solid foundation to implement the different activities planned in the next period, which are expected to yield positive results that will contribute to the successful delivery of the project objectives.